

Teacher Professional Competencies In Ap Residential Schools: In The Area Of Parent-Community Co-Ordination

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Abstract

In the state of Andhra Pradesh, Government managed Residential Schools are considered as modern institutions to develop the children who are economically, socially backward, and scarred inhabitants in remote hilly areas. The quality of school education plays a crucial role in social transformation. Further, the quality of school education majorly depends on the competencies of teachers. Professional competencies of a teacher include pedagogical, cultural, communicational, personal, intellectual, etc. which are needed for effective teaching-learning.

The present paper is a study on the professional competencies of teachers in Government managed residential schools in north coastal Andhra Pradesh in the area of parent/community coordination.

Introduction

The development of any country mainly depends on maintaining internal peace and harmony. Peace and harmony can be sustained only when there are equal opportunities in every sector for their people. Despite many developmental schemes and programs run by both state and central governments, tribal communities in India are still under vulnerable conditions. Some people belong to backward classes and scheduled castes are still facing challenges to coup up with the recent developments of the society. Hence, a strong foundation of education through skill development will significantly bring the desired transformation in the society. However, the quality of school education primarily depends on the professional competencies of the teacher..

Significance Of The Study

Government managed Residential Schools are instrumental in developing the children who are economically, socially backward, and scarred inhabitants in remote hilly areas of Andhra Pradesh. The quality of school education plays a crucial role in social transformation. However, the quality of school education majorly depends on the competencies of teachers. Professional competencies of a teacher include pedagogical, cultural, communicational, personal, intellectual, etc. which are needed for effective teaching-learning.

The present paper is a study on the professional competencies of teachers in Government managed residential schools in north coastal Andhra Pradesh is an attempt to bring new facts. The professional competencies are segregated into nine areas in line with the guidelines of NCERT and however the present paper deals with professional competencies in the area of parent/community coordination. The finding of the study will be beneficial to all stake holders of residential schools viz., teachers, parents and head of institution, curriculum developer, and administration in doing their respective job.

Review Of Literature

Many researchers worked on the professional competencies of teachers. The relationship between professional competencies of Iranian teachers and their perspectives about the qualitative evaluation project is presented by (Ilanlou & Zand, 2011). Recent research on the professional competencies of mathematics teachers, which has been carried out during the last decade, is characterized by different theoretical approaches on the conceptualization and evaluation of teachers' professional competencies, namely cognitive versus situated approaches by (Blmeke & Kaiser, 2017; Kaiser et al., 2017).The teachers' training and professional competencies is studied by (Kulshrestha & Pandey, 2013), and the professional competency of teachers in terms of social, personnel and contextual situations (Kulshrestha & Pandey, 2013) and same line these competencies are related to student achievement in (Olaleye, 2013). A study on vignette testing to measure student science

teachers' professional competencies is done by (Brovelli et al., 2014). Some of the researchers (Zaragoza et al., 2021) worked on the teacher of the 21st century: professional competencies in Catalonia today.

More recently (Ziden et al., 2020) worked on the use of Mobile Instant Messaging for Parent-Teacher Communication. Teacher competencies in implementing collaborative learning and their dependence on interaction with the students is focused in (Kaendler et al., 2015), The readiness of Training Institution in Preparing Teacher Competencies is done by (Kusumaningtyas et al., 2020) and is focused on achievement of competence level as a teacher in the physics education study program. The study on “Knowledge, skills, and attitudes as predictors in determining teachers' competency in Malaysian TVET institutions” is done by (Omar et al., 2020) is created interest among the educationalists in the Malaysia. Similarly there are many works on recently presented on professional competencies (Dusadee & Piriyasurawong, 2020; Efimova et al., 2021; Tambunan et al., 2021; Ziden et al., 2020). The teacher professional skills required in 21st century has been presented in (Zaragoza et al., 2021). Special professional competencies for teaching mathematics and other courses are done in (Kaiser et al., 2017) and qualitative evaluation is done by (Ilanlou & Zand, 2011). The studies on community practice and culture development by teachers are presented by (Borg, 2012; Patton & Parker, 2017; Printy, 2008). There are some important works presented in (Callaghan & Mizzi, 2015; Laitsch et al., 2021; Viczko et al., 2019) for understanding the role of teacher in community.

Objectives Of The Study

The aim of the present study is to explore professional competencies of teachers in Government managed residential schools in north coastal Andhra Pradesh in the area of parent/community coordination. More specifically

- To collect the opinion of the sample respondents on professional competencies of teachers of residential schools in north coastal Andhra Pradesh.
- To study the specific professional competency significantly resulting in parent/community-coordination in government-managed residential schools of North coastal Andhra Pradesh.

Methodology

In the present work, to examine the impact of demographic variables on the professional competencies of teachers especially in Parent-community co-ordination of government-managed residential schools in North coastal Andhra Pradesh, primary data has been thoroughly evaluated to determine if there is any variation in the teachers' (respondent's) opinion on it.

Variables of the study

1. Gender	Male / Female
2. Age (in Years)	Below 35 / 35 to 45 / Above 45
3. The locality of the School	Rural/Urban/Tribal
4. Type of School Management	APSW / APBCW/ APTW School
5. General Qualifications	B.A., / B.SC./ M.A., / M.Sc., /Others.
6. Professional Qualifications	B.Ed. / M.Ed.
7. Teaching Experience (years)	Below 10 / 10 to 20 / Above 20
8. Teaching Subject	Mathematics/Science/Social/Language

Sample

The researcher adopted a simple random sampling technique in selecting the schools. The researcher selected a total of 26 schools in Srikakulam; Vizianagaram and Visakhapatnam districts were selected covering rural, urban, and tribal management.

Tool of the study

A tool was prepared by selecting nine components. It is into 9 different areas such as – 1) Supporting for Learning, 2) Maintaining an Effective Learning Environment, 3) Organizing Subject Matter for Student Learning, 4) Planning for Teaching, 5) Assessment, 6) Professionalism, 7) Co-curricular & Extra Curricular Activities, 8) Teaching Learning Material and 9) Parent/Community Co-ordination. However, in the present work, the questioner is customized to meet the research objectives based on the (i) Professional competencies by NCTE (1998) document and Professional competencies by suggested by Bürgener and his team (2018).

Analysis And Interpretation

Following table shows the respondent's opinion on parent/community-coordination in government-managed residential schools of North coastal Andhra Pradesh. The Fig.1 to Fig.4 shows the mean comparison of all independent variables.

Table.1 Analysis of the respondent's opinion

S.No	Statement	Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
01	Maintaining relationships with the staff, students parents, etc.	224	95.73	7	2.99	3	1.28
02	Information of parents about the discipline of their children in the PTA meetings.	213	91.03	17	7.26	4	1.71
03	Encouraging the parents for the maintenance of cooperation.	212	90.60	19	8.12	3	1.28
04	Lack of encouragement from parents in the proper maintenance of school	202	86.32	17	7.26	15	6.41
05	Encouraging the parents for participation in the school meeting.	202	86.32	28	11.97	4	1.71
06	Extending support by the parents is not encouraging in making the maximum student enrolment and retention at school level.	193	82.48	28	11.97	13	5.56
07	Discussing issues related to student achievement in the SMC meeting.	211	90.17	20	8.55	3	1.28
08	Communicating the progress of students to their parents.	210	89.74	23	9.83	1	0.43
09	Working with SMC and parents to improve professional practice in the school	199	85.04	34	14.53	1	0.43
10	Making effective use of teachers' parents' conferences.	202	86.32	31	13.25	1	0.43
11	Maintaining good contacts with parents to building strong working relationships.	215	91.88	18	7.69	1	0.43
12	Utilizing the grants allocated under various schemes properly with the consultation of SMC	216	92.31	17	7.26	1	0.43

- It is observed that 95.73 % of teachers expressed that, maintaining relationships with the staff, students' parents, etc.
- About 91.03 % of teachers expressed that, information of parents about the discipline of their children in the PTA meetings and very less number of students disagreed.
- It is noticed that 90.60 % of teachers expressed that, encouraging the parents for the maintenance of cooperation whereas 8.12 % of the teachers undecided and 1.28 % of the teachers disagreed.
- It is noticed that 86.32 % of teachers expressed that, lack of encouragement from parents in the proper maintenance of school
- It is noticed that 86.32 % of teachers expressed that, encouraging the parents to participate in the school meeting and 1.71 % of the teachers disagreed.
- It is noticed that 82.48 % of teachers expressed that, extending support by the parents is not encouraging in making the maximum student enrolment and retention at the school level whereas 11.97 % of the teachers undecided and 5.56 % of the teachers disagreed.
- It is noticed that 90.17 % of teachers expressed that, discussing issues related to student achievement in the SMC meeting whereas 8.55 % of the teachers undecided and 1.28 % of the teachers disagreed.

- It is observed that 89.74 % of teachers expressed that, communicating the progress of students to their parents whereas 9.83 % of the teachers undecided and 0.43 % of the teachers disagreed.
- It is observed that 85.04 % of teachers expressed that, working with SMC and parents to improve professional practice in the school.
- It is noticed that 86.32% of teachers expressed that, making effective use of teachers' parents' conferences whereas 13.25% of the teachers undecided and 0.43 % of the teachers disagreed.
- It is noticed that 91.88 % of teachers expressed that, maintaining good contacts with parents to building strong working relationships whereas 7.69 % of the teachers undecided and 0.43 % of the teachers disagreed.

It is noticed that 92.31 % of teachers expressed that, utilizing the grants allocated under various schemes properly.

Table.2 Mean, SD, and 't'/'F'- values on the perceptions of teachers based on their socio-economic variables with respect to Parent / Community Co-Ordination

Variable	Category	N	Mean	SD	t' / 'F'-Value	p-value
Gender	Male	154	49.61	4.93	3.69**	0.00
	Female	80	52.05	4.53		
Age (in Years)	Below 35	52	51.47	5.37	3.04*	0.05
	35 to 45	83	50.87	4.58		
	Above 45	99	49.57	4.86		
Locality	Rural	120	50.05	5.28	2.84*	0.05
	Urban	36	50.30	4.65		
	Tribal	78	52.08	3.95		
Management	AP Social Welfare	133	50.38	4.82	0.45 ^{NS}	0.64
	AP BC Welfare	39	51.90	3.60		
	AP Tribal Welfare	62	50.39	5.25		
General Qualification	B.A.,	25	49.21	5.26	0.88 ^{NS}	0.45
	B.Sc.,	50	51.12	4.58		
	M.A.,	79	50.59	5.20		
	M.Sc.,	80	50.25	4.76		
Professional Qualification	B.Ed.,	221	50.56	4.90	1.98*	0.05
	M.Ed.,	13	47.25	4.95		
Teaching Experience(In years)	Below 10	78	51.15	5.51	1.56 ^{NS}	0.21
	10 to 20	120	50.27	4.64		
	Above 20	36	49.49	4.38		
Teaching Subject	Mathematics	60	50.60	4.70	0.03 ^{NS}	0.99
	Science	60	50.45	5.00		
	Social Studies	46	50.33	5.46		
	Language	68	50.38	4.78		

- It is observed that the mean perceptual scores of teachers with respect to Parent / Community Co-Ordination. The mean perceptual score of male category respondents is 49.61; whereas it

is for the female category respondents is 52.05. The derived t – value is 3.69 and the p -value is 0.00 which was statistically significant at 0.01 level. This shows that male and female category respondents differed significantly in their perceptions and female category respondents expressed high perceptions towards Parent / Community Co-Ordination than that of male category teachers.

- The mean perceptual scores of teachers for below 35 years age group is 51.47, whereas it is for 35 to 45 years age group is 50.87 and it is for above 45 years age group is 49.57. The ‘F’-value is 3.04 and the p -value is 0.05, which is statistically significant at 0.05 level. This shows that age group category respondents differed significantly and below 35 years age group teachers expressed high perceptions towards Parent / Community Co-Ordination than that of 35 to 45 and above 45 years age group teachers.
- The mean perceptual scores of teachers belong to a rural area is 50.05 whereas it is for the urban and tribal is 50.30 and 52.08 respectively. The ‘F’-value is 2.84 and the p -value is 0.05 which is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This shows that there is a significant difference among the perceptions of teachers based on their locality and tribal area category teachers expressed high perceptions towards Parent / Community Co-Ordination than that of rural and urban area category teachers.
- The mean perceptual scores of teachers working in AP, Social Welfare schools is 50.38, whereas it is for the AP BC Welfare Schools is 51.90 and it is for the AP Tribal Welfare Schools is 50.39 respectively. The ‘F’-value is 0.45 and the p -value is 0.64 which is statistically not significant at any level. This shows that there is no significant difference among the perceptions of teachers based on their school management and they expressed similar opinion towards Parent / Community Co-Ordination.
- The mean perceptual score of B.A., qualified category respondents is 49.21, it is for B.Sc., qualified category respondents is 51.12, it is for M.A., qualified category teachers is 50.59, whereas it is for M.Sc., qualified category respondents is 50.25. The derived F – value is 0.88 and the p -value is 0.45, which is statistically not significant at any level. This shows that all the categories of teachers basing on their educational qualifications did not differ significantly and they expressed similar opinion towards Parent / Community Co-Ordination.
- The mean perceptual score of B.Ed., qualified category respondents were 50.56 whereas it is for M.Ed., qualified category teachers is 47.25. The derived t – value is 1.98 and the p -value is 0.05, which is statistically significant at 0.05 level. This shows that all the categories of teachers based on their professional qualifications differed significantly and B.Ed., qualified category teachers expressed high perceptions towards Parent / Community Co-Ordination than that of M.Ed., qualified category teachers.
- The mean perceptual score of teachers for below 10 years’ experience category is 51.15 whereas it is for the 10 to 20 years teaching experience category teachers is 50.27 and it is for above 20 years teaching experience category teachers is 49.49. The derived F – value is 1.56 and the p -value is 0.21 which is not significant. This shows that, all the teacher category respondents based on their teaching experience did not differ significantly in their perceptions and they expressed similar opinion towards Parent / Community Co-Ordination.
- The mean perceptual score of teachers for Mathematics teaching subject is 50.60 whereas it is for the Science subject teaching teachers is 50.45 and it is for Social Studies teaching subject teachers is 50.33 and it is for Language teaching subject teachers is 50.38. The derived F – value is 0.03 and the p -value is 0.99 which is not significant. This shows that, all the teacher category respondents based on their teaching subject did not differ significantly in their perceptions and they expressed similar opinion towards Parent / Community Co-Ordination.
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Fig.1 the perceptions of teachers based on their Gender and Age

Fig.2. the perceptions of teachers based on their Locality and Management

Fig.3 the perceptions of teachers based on their General and Professional Qualification.

Fig.4 perceptions of teachers based on their Teaching Experience and Teaching Subject

Suggestions

The teachers should be more proactive in sharing information about their students' attendance and formative assessment results through mobile communication. They should invite the parents and community while organizing national festivals, annual days, and other significant meetings. The success of the students in public examinations and other competitive examinations are needed to be celebrated with the community and parents. The strong parent-teacher association can bring laurels to the school and the success to their students.

Conclusion

The present paper deals with a study on Professional Competencies of Teachers in AP Residential Schools, in the area of Parent-community co-ordination. The study is mainly in line with NCERT guidelines on professional competencies. The results of the present work demonstrated significant influence by all the proposed independent variables. The continuous development programs, workshops, and other training programs are necessary to improve the parent/community co-ordination. Some special training programs are to be facilitated for the teachers to use web tools and mobile apps for sharing information with the parents and community.

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